

The Effect That Participation in Combat Sports Has on An Athlete's Brain Health

Dating back to the Roman Empire, people would enjoy watching gladiators fight in the colosseum. People would consider this to be entertainment. Despite this, some of the gladiator fights would result in death for the loser, and the crowd failed to consider the fighters' health. This is also relevant today, with fighters facing long-term risks to their brain like Alzheimer's. These brain effects are caused early on but can show up much later in life. For example, Alzheimer's symptoms show up twenty years after the brain change happens (Alzheimer's Association 70). Many fighters experience negative effects on their brain health. People who watch combat sports like boxing and MMA fail to consider the risks that fighters face on a daily basis. Some of the risks that fighters face include negative brain effects like decreased brain size and slower mental speeds (Dixon 366). Fighters face many risks from getting consistently hit in the head and experiencing brain trauma. This is important to fighters throughout their entire life because the brain trauma they get will affect their entire life. Also, boxing can cause chronic brain injury and death (Rudd 1). These negative effects impact many boxers throughout the world, not just a few. This is shown by a study done on 244 boxers, where 37 of them had signs of chronic traumatic brain injury. With many combat sport athletes showing signs of chronic traumatic brain injuries, boxers are at serious risk of experiencing long term effects to the brain health, like Chronic Traumatic Encephalopathy (CTE). CTE is a degenerative brain disorder which is more common in athletes with a history of brain trauma (Field and Logan 45). In addition to CTE, another long-lasting brain effect that fighters may experience is dementia. Repeated brain injuries increase the risk of dementia (Alzheimer's Society). Alzheimer's disease is a type of brain disease that damages neurons in the brain. The neurons that are damaged first

are responsible for memory, language and thinking (Alzheimer's Association 70). These findings lead to my question of: How does participation in combat sports negatively impact an athlete's brain health? Participation in combat sports negatively affects an athlete's brain health significantly with long-lasting brain effects. This impacts the athlete, doctors, and the coach.

Combat sport athletes must be protected and kept safe while they compete in the sport they love. Combat sport athletes must also be aware of their personal health. Combat sports commonly cause severe injuries more than any other popular sport. Up to one-half of fights in combat sports cause an injury to the athlete, many of which being to the head and neck (Seifert). Because of this statistic, fighters must work hard to protect their brain since they compete in such dangerous sports. In addition, combat sports are inherently dangerous to fighters' brains, and there has been no change to this. Studies have estimated that 20-50% of former boxers have symptoms of chronic brain injury (Seifert). Many boxers throughout history have shown to have brain injuries, which shows a consistent impact on their brains throughout time. This can also negatively impact boxers mentally, with fighters being forced to retire because of brain injuries. For example, former professional boxing champion Darron Mcdermott was forced to retire because of a ruptured brain aneurysm, which caused him to undergo an emergency surgery, and the result of this injury was permanent brain damage (Irwinmitchell). Because of fighters like Mcdermott being forced to retire due to brain injuries, as well as these injuries lasting later in life, many fighters are left with impacts to their mental health as they battle their physical challenges. These fighters are left feeling nostalgic and incomplete as they are physically unable to compete in their sport. The feeling of nostalgia comes because people are more familiar with challenges from the past than the challenges they face now, and they look back on the past

fondly compared to the present (Norberg 12). This is why many fighters will look back on their careers with nostalgia. In addition, this feeling is amplified as not only are fighters looking back on their old careers, but they are also looking back on their old selves as brain damage changes personality, emotions, and thinking. This is shown in the Mcdermott case as his brain damage caused short-term memory loss and struggles with aggression control (Irwinmitchell). Since the brain damage that fighters get impacts their emotions as well as cognitive thinking, it makes sense why many fighters miss their old life that they were able to live. Brain damage affects a fighter mentally and physically, and it is also extremely detrimental to a fighter's emotional state. Not only does fighting cause brain damage that can affect fighters later in life, but fighting can also cause brain damage so severe that it results in death. For example, John Cooney, an Irish boxer, died at 28 just one month ago after suffering an intracranial hemorrhage during a knockout loss (Sealey). Brain effects to fighters can impact them physically, with the impact being as severe as death. Brain effects can also impact fighters emotionally and mentally, as brain damage changes a fighter's thinking and personality, which often leads to negative nostalgic feelings among former fighters.

The negative brain effects that fighters experience also impact doctors, because doctors must be able to identify potential health risks that their patients may have, especially for combat sport athletes. It is as important as ever for doctors to protect fighters' brain health. This is because the number of people aged 65 and older with Alzheimer's is projected to increase from 6.1 million in 2020 to 13.8 million in 2060 (Alzheimer's Association 72). Doctors need to be very responsible when treating patients that participate in combat sports so that they do not get long term brain effects. This is why the Canadian Pediatric Society and American Academy of

Pediatrics recommend that a ringside physician is present at all amateur boxing matches, and that the physician can stop the fight at any time (Lee 170). This shows the extremely important role that doctors have in preserving the health and safety of combat sports athletes. To show this further, doctor intervention in combat sports can prevent long-term cognitive and mental health effects in athletes that would not stop fighting before a doctor steps in. This is because combat sports athletes will continue to participate in their sport despite injuries that they may have. Athletes that rest when they are injured are often looked down upon while athletes who push through injuries are praised (AlHashmi 12). This fact of athletes pushing themselves while having injuries is significantly more dangerous for combat sports athletes. Around 6.9 million Americans are living with Alzheimer's dementia (Alzheimer's Association 70). Out of these 6.9 million people, former boxers are 4.1 times more likely to get Alzheimer's than the average person (Batty et al 1). This is why it is so important for doctors to protect combat sport athletes and prevent them from pushing themselves and risking their health. If fighters specifically are not given proper treatment as well as stern advice from doctors, they are at a serious risk of having long term brain health effects like Alzheimer's. Aside from physical doctors, psychiatrists can also be very helpful with combat sports athletes, especially after the fighter has retired. When combat sport athletes are unable to compete, it is very common for them to suffer with mental health issues. For example, Leslie Hernandez, an MMA fighter, dealt with anxiety, depression, and guilt when she was unable to compete due to injuries (Hadley). After fighters retire, they experience these same mental health struggles. It is extremely important for psychiatrists to notice mental struggles that fighters may face and give them treatment. Mental health is not a commonly talked about issue in the combat sports world, especially where head

trauma is extremely common (Robb-Dover). A career of fighting can have many effects on a fighter's health, in more ways than just physical effects. Doctors must pick up on signs of mental health issues before they start severely affecting the fighter. This is because when a fighter starts showing significant signs of mental health problems, severe damage could've already occurred (Robb-Dover). Doctors hold such a significant responsibility in managing a fighter's health, and it is extremely important for doctors to pick on signs of mental/brain health issues as well as restricting a fighter from fighting to prevent further brain damage.

Coaches are also a huge part of a fighter's brain health. This is because coaches are someone that manages a fighter and must protect their health at all times. Coaches also must be responsible enough to stop a fighter when they see signs of brain trauma occurring. In the mental health aspect, coaches are someone who fighters are very close to and should feel comfortable enough to talk to about mental health struggles. This is extremely important for combat sports athletes as fighters may not have many other people to talk to about these struggles. This deep connection between coaches and fighters can help coaches make fighters remember the career they've had to feel positively. People in struggling times can be helped when they remember better days from the past (Norberg 10). This is extremely important in fighters as they have been shown to have many mental health struggles, especially later in their career where it is even more important to look back fondly on the career they've had. In addition, fighters are shown to have a much higher chance of having Dementia or Alzheimer's, and this nostalgia of looking back on their career can help dementia sufferers establish a sense of personal continuity (Norberg 10). This shows that a coach helping their combat sport athlete mentally will also help them physically, which shows a direct effect in the mental and physical brain effects in fighters.

Furthermore, the mental impact that coaches can have on their fighters is clear when looking at the success fighters have when they have a strong connection with their coaches. A good coaching perspective and effective coaching plans affect an athlete's performance significantly (Spencer 61). This shows that coaches can affect an athlete's mental health in such a positive way that they will experience positive effects on their physical brain health as well as their performance in their sport. Coaches are one of the most significant figures in an athlete's mental health.

To summarize, participation in combat sports can affect an athlete's mental health in many different ways. This includes physical brain risks and chronic brain disorders like Chronic Traumatic Encephalopathy (CTE), Dementia, and Alzheimer's. The effects that this has on combat sports athlete's cognitive function includes memory loss, difficulty thinking, and brain fog. In addition to physical brain effects, combat sports athletes are at risk of suffering from mental health effects like depression, anxiety, and guilt when they are unable to fight or lose a fight. In addition to long term physical effects, fighting can have severe, unexpected physical brain effects that can result in death. For example, John Cooney, an Irish boxer, died from suffering an intracranial hemorrhage during a knockout loss. This shows that fighters experience significant brain effects that are extremely unpredictable, which makes it even more important for fighters to be protected. This issue affects fighters, doctors, and coaches. Fighters are directly affected as they need to be aware of symptoms they may face and be responsible to protect their personal health. Doctors are also affected by this because they must be responsible in consistently tracking and checking the health of fighters to prevent significant brain issues. Doctors also must be responsible enough to force a fighter to rest when they need to, because it

is shown that most athletes will try to push through their injuries and it is generally looked down upon in the fighting world to pull out of fights due to injuries, which can cause fighters to fight with brain injuries like concussions unless a doctor intervenes. Doctors are also important to fighters after their career, when many former fighters may have Alzheimer's. An important part of treating a person with Alzheimer's is ensuring they take medication (Alzheimer's Association 72). Because of this, doctors are extremely important in maintaining a fighter's health during their entire life, since the brain effects they get can affect fighters for the rest of their life. Finally, coaches are significantly affected in the mental health area because they have the closest bond to fighters, and the lessons they can show their fighters are shown to be able to have significant positive impacts on the fighters' mental health.

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